

BORROWINGS FROM NATIVE AMERICAN LANGUAGES INTO ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Abduraxmonova Zilola

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages
2-course master

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Abstract: The collection of loanwords that gets imported into the lexicon of each language concerned is one of the most immediately evident effects of intercultural contact and communication. Over the last fifty years, the area of cultures and languages in touch has expanded dramatically. From the beginning, a 'Scale' or 'Index of Receptivity' has been proposed for languages that take borrowings more readily. A 'Scale of Adaptability' has been proposed in addition to that scale. The study of a language's flexibility and receptivity to borrowed terms, particularly those from International English, yields several fascinating case studies. Major languages such as English, Spanish, Japanese, and Chinese serve as useful case studies for discussing adaptation and receptivity indices.

Key words: borrowings, English language, culture, communication, vocabulary.

English is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world. Its history is fascinating for a variety of reasons, including its adaptability to borrowing from other languages, which has broadened its vocabulary throughout the years. Many research on these foreign features in English have been conducted. Jespersen's book on the history and development of English laid the groundwork for many people to do their own research on loanwords in English.

Borrowing results through cultural interaction between two language populations. Word borrowing can occur in both ways between two languages in touch, although there is generally an imbalance, with more words flowing from one side to the other. In this situation, the source language community has some advantage in terms of power, status, and/or income, which makes the goods and ideas brought by the source language community appealing and helpful to the borrowing language community. For example, in the first several decades A.D., the Germanic tribes absorbed numerous loanwords from Latin as they acquired new items through commerce with the Romans. However, only a few Germanic terms made it into Latin.

The history starts Celtic speakers who were conquered by the Romans about a half century BC. Latin was the language of England for centuries until various Germanic tribes – the Angles, Saxons, and Jutes – began to enter England in some numbers in the 5th century. These Germanic speakers borrowed few of the Celtic words; other Celtic lexical borrowings (also called loanwords or loans) came later, such as: clan, colleen, leprechaun, shillelagh, and slogan. In the earliest centuries "English" was the Germanic language brought over, one which already had identifiable loanwords when it arrived in England. Many Latin words were in the vocabulary, such as wine (L. vinum) and calic (L. calicem, now chalice). The adoption of many words relating to cooking suggests the wholesale adoption of Roman food preparation: cook (L. coquus), kitchen (L. coquina), and foods such as pear, peach, plum, beet, mint, pepper, and so on.

After St. Augustine visited England in 597 AD and Christianized the kingdom, the next important effect on English happened. Many Church-related Latin terms entered the vernacular before Augustine, but the majority later. Among the early borrowings were church, minister, demon, and angel. Along with the religion, the Church system's vocabulary was adopted: pope, bishop, priest, monk, nun, Mass, and many more.

Scandinavians ("Vikings") conducted modest incursions on England towards the end of the eighth century, followed by colonization. During the next centuries, many place names, personal names, and general terminology from Scandinavian languages (Danish, Norwegian) were established. These speakers' linguistic borrowings are intriguing since they are sometimes borrowings of the "identical" term decades later. [These reborrowings are technically known as doublets.] For example, the Scandinavian *skyrta* was derived from the Old English *scyrte* ("shirt") ("skirt"). The two versions developed to imply distinct styles of clothing.

The Normans (French) were the next wave of invaders, representing a more polished civilization. For a few centuries beginning in 1066 AD, French became the language of government and the elite classes in English society. Except for OE king and queen, virtually all modern English terms linked to governance are borrowed from French, including govern(ment), rule, and monarch.

The English borrowed the most titles in terms of social standing, court titles, and the like: duke, marquis, baron, countess, court, and nobility. The French advanced military dominance is reflected in the widespread use of military terminology such as war, peace, officer, lieutenant, sergeant, soldier, and admiral.

Even though Danish law had previously offered some English terminology, French control provided some essential legal words, such as court, jury, judge, defendant, and attorney.

French, a descendent of Latin, added another layer of Latin-derived borrowings to the lexicon of religion: religion, savior, trinity, angel, saint, and a slew of other terms. Food produces a rather unique and occasionally humorous outcome. The animals, which have English names: cow, sheep, swine, and deer, were cared for by the lower classes. Meat with French names appeared on the owner's table as food: beef/veal, mutton, pork/bacon, and venison. However, in the early stages of the French occupation, upper-class English did not employ many French vocabulary in their written English.

Latin had an influence during the Renaissance since it had been the language of study in Europe for many centuries. Latin, and to a lesser extent its sister classical language, Greek, have been a constant source of loanwords since the 14th century. The most apparent locations to observe Latin borrowings in English are in biology, botany, and chemical terminology. The taxonomy and accessible compound terms are both derived from Latin. The majority of the world's scientific community considers Latin to be the global language (or, at the very least, nomenclature) of science.

Thousands of terms from foreign languages were borrowed and formed part of the English vocabulary when English traders expanded throughout the globe during the maritime centuries. Several dictionaries reflect the later condition of borrowings into English.

English in North America

The growth of American English added words that enriched the lexicon from other sources. Various Native American ("Indian") languages have contributed words, as have the Black

Americans. Native American (various tribes): bayou, caribou, hickory, hogan, hominy, igloo, lagniappe, moccasin, moose, muskrat, opossum, pecan, persimmon Black American: banjo, goober, gorilla, gumbo, jazz, jigger, juke Mexico has contributed not only Spanish words in a variety of meaning areas such as the cattle industry and food, but also words from the native languages of Mexico as well. Mexico has reinforced the Spanish loans and has contributed vocabulary from the indigenous population. Of especial interest are those loans associated with the cattle industry and the Southwest U.S.A. The horsemanship of the early cattle industry was largely learned from the Mexican experts and the cuisine of the Southwest borrowed most of the items and terminology of Mexican cooking. Mexican: adobe, bronco, burro, canyon, chile, chocolate, cinch, coyote, frijole, hacienda, pinto, pueblo, ocelot, poncho, rodeo, serape, stampede, taco, tamale, tomato, tortilla, vamoose The lexicon of American English contains words that can be traced back to over one hundred languages. Given that speakers from more and more countries are immigrating to the US, many more of the world's languages may contribute loanwords as well

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